

HIGHER EDUCATION MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: This article talks about the structure and system of higher education management, goals and tasks.

Key words: Higher education institution, rector, pedagogy, practice, specialist, educational program

It is known that higher education institutions are the leading link of the educational system. It is the task of the higher education system to train qualified specialists who are educated in all respects, have high potential, cultural and moral qualities. In order for personnel who graduated from higher education institutions to be able to work in an enterprise or organization in their field in the future, the educational institution should provide students with sufficient knowledge and skills. We also believe that students should work on themselves, act independently, and sharpen their knowledge. What are the main tasks of the higher education system? Therefore, the following are the main tasks of the higher education system:

- *ensuring quality education based on modern educational and professional programs in accordance with state educational standards;*
- *training of highly qualified scientific-pedagogical personnel, including in foreign scientific centers;*

Individualization of education, introduction of new pedagogical and information technologies and tools of distance education;

- *putting into practice methods of effective combination of education, science and production;*
- *development of mutually beneficial relations with developed countries in the field of higher education; [1:34]*

And it consists of many other similar tasks. The effective solution of the above-mentioned tasks depends on the management system of the higher education system and its constituent units (university, academy, institute, etc.). Persons engaged in management in the field of higher education should have a high level of responsibility, authority, and the ability to regularly and effectively assess administrative rules using internal and external means.[2:37] Higher education institutions are directly managed by a rector appointed by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In non-state HEIs, the rector is appointed by the founder.

The rector is responsible for the work results of the educational institution in accordance with the statute "On Higher Education". In accordance with the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, he acts on behalf of the educational institution, represents it with all agencies, institutions and enterprises, disposes of property, concludes contracts, issues a power of

attorney, opens an account number of the educational institution in the bank, distributes loans. .so, the rector is the person who organizes the management activities of the HEI.

Rectot issues orders for all employees, students and other learners within the scope of its authority and determines the powers of organizations and departments that are part of scientific research, experiment and other educational institutions, workers, servants, as well as , the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan hires and dismisses scientific-pedagogical staff and performs other powers in accordance with the law.

It is known that our system of higher education is changing and developing significantly. State management of the education system is carried out in accordance with the main principles of state policy in the field of education through the relevant articles of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education". The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" states that the management of the education sector in Uzbekistan is carried out by the higher government under the jurisdiction of the Republic and its management bodies. The Ministry of Public Education, the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education are the highest state bodies of education management in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

As mentioned above, a number of activities have been carried out and are being improved in the development of the higher education system. In particular, according to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5847 of October 8, 2019, the Concept of the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 was approved.

This concept aims to improve the quality of education, train competitive personnel, effectively organize scientific and innovative activities, international in order to develop cooperation, as well as in connection with the implementation of the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4391 of July 11, 2019 "On measures to introduce new principles of management into the system of higher and secondary special education" developed. In the concept, in order to modernize higher education and develop social spheres and economic sectors based on advance development of public-private partnership in the field of higher education, increasing the level of coverage with higher education from 50 percent based on the organization of activities of state and non-state higher education institutions in the regions, creating a healthy competitive environment in the field;

Turning the National University of Uzbekistan and Samarkand State University into the flagship of our country's higher education institutions;

at least 10 higher education institutions in the republic are included in the list of higher education institutions in the first 1,000 places of the ranking of internationally recognized organizations (Quacquarelli Symonds World University Rankings, Times Nearer Education or Academic Ranking of World Universities), including National University of Uzbekistan and Samarkand State University in the list of the first 500 higher education institutions;

step-by-step transfer of the educational process to the credit-module system in higher education institutions;d educational technologies:

based on international experiences, introduction of advanced standards of higher education, including a gradual transition from education focused on acquiring theoretical knowledge to an educational system focused on the formation of practical skills in educational programs;

to raise the content of higher education to a new level in terms of quality, to establish a system of training highly qualified personnel who can make a worthy contribution to the sustainable

development of the social sphere and economic sectors, and who can find their place in the labor market;

ensuring academic independence of higher education institutions;

step-by-step introduction of the "University 3.0" concept, which provides for the interdependence of education, science, innovation and commercialization of research results in higher education institutions;

attracting foreign investments, expanding the scope of paid services and establishing technoparks, foresights, technology transfer, start-up, accelerator centers in higher education institutions at the expense of other extra-budgetary funds, and their socio-economic development of the relevant industry, sector and regions bringing it to the level of research and forecasting scientific-practical institutions; [3:lex.uz]

The publication of articles by professors and teachers of higher education institutions, researchers, doctoral students, undergraduate and graduate students in prestigious international scientific journals with a high impact factor, increasing the citation rate of articles, as well as the promotion of republican scientific journals to international scientific and technical standards. ensure that the database is entered step-by-step and a number of similar innovations have been introduced and are being implemented. In particular, the transition to the credit-module system made it more convenient for teachers and students.

It is worth mentioning that our education system may be lagging behind the education system of many developed countries today. However, the new Uzbekistan is going through a phase of development and growth. In the near future. We hope that the quality of education and the issue of qualified personnel will certainly record positive results. Our ancestors are children of a great country, and we should live a life worthy of it.

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